

The Influence of Entrepreneurial Characteristics on Innovation Capability through Organizational Learning Capability as an Intervening Variable

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

This research can provide a paradigm shift for business people, in order to develop a business so that it can be managed properly. This study aims to determine the effect of entrepreneurial characteristics on innovation capability through organizational learning capability. The research was conducted on small and medium enterprises (SMEs) which are cafe owners in the city of Bandung.

The data collection technique used in this research is primary data through questionnaires. The sampling technique used is non-probability sampling, with a convenience sampling technique obtained as many as 60 cafe owners spread across the city of Bandung, while the analysis technique used is descriptive verification with structural equation modeling (SEM) analysis method with partial least squares (PLS).

Based on the results of data research, it was found that the level of entrepreneurial characteristics, learning capability and innovation capability were in the fairly good category. The results of hypothesis testing show that there is an influence of entrepreneurial characteristics on organizational learning capability, there is an influence of entrepreneurial characteristics on innovation capability, there is an influence of organizational learning capability on innovation capability and there is an influence of entrepreneurial characteristics on innovation capability through organizational learning capability. This proves that organizational learning capability is an intervening variable that can mediate the effect of entrepreneurial characteristics on innovation capability in Cafe Owners in Bandung City.

Keywords: CHARACTERISTICS OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP, INNOVATION CAPABILITY, ORGANIZATIONAL LEARNING CAPABILITY, UMKM

Introduction

Micro, small and medium enterprises are one of the drivers in improving the economy both in Indonesia and ASEAN. Job opportunities that arise from the business group is considered far greater than the absorption of labor performed by big business, with the amount of absorption of energy work that is carried out by SMEs, the role of strategic against government efforts to reduce poverty in the country. Around 88% to 99% of business forms in ASEAN are micro, small and medium enterprises by contributing to gross

domestic product (GDP) of around 30% to 57% and employment of 50% to 97%. In Indonesia was recorded in the year 2018 as many as 64.19 million units of effort which stood 99.9% of them are SMEs by contributing to the GDP amounted to 57.24% and assist in employment of up to 97%. Seeing from these figures, the role of SMEs is felt to be very instrumental in helping to create jobs, so as to reduce the number of unemployed and can help encourage economic growth both at the national and regional levels.

The city of Bandung as one of the largest cities in Indonesia cannot be separated from the phenomenon of the proliferation of SMEs, as a city that has many backgrounds both in terms of culture, industry, activities, and education, the city of Bandung has a society that tends to be heterogeneous. The economic structure of the people of Bandung varies, consisting of the lower, middle, and upper classes. There are also quite a variety of community activities, ranging from entrepreneurs, employees, employees, students, to university students. This is also the background for the development of various SME businesses according to the market they want to target. The city of Bandung itself has given birth to various types of businesses that produce products by managing existing resources. In its journey, SMEs in the city of Bandung are used as SME centers which are the center of business activities in certain areas/locations. The city of Bandung is not only known for its shopping area, but it is also famous for its culinary tourism. Starting from typical Sundanese snacks, as well as snacks sold at roadside stalls. Currently, there are many places to eat that not only sell food, but also sell a unique concept of a place that attracts the attention of visitors both from the city of Bandung itself, and from outside the city of Bandung. The economic shift in the city of Bandung from an industrial city to a service city is shown by the increasing contribution of the trade, hotel and restaurant sectors to the economy of the city of Bandung. Gross regional domestic product (GDP) is the total value added of goods and services generated from all economic activities in all regions within a certain year period, generally within one year.

One of the businesses in the restaurant sector is a cafe. This cafe industry is a restaurant business, which carries a modern concept and becomes a promising business opportunity in the city of Bandung. The business opportunity in the cafe business is an inspiration for entrepreneurs or entrepreneurs who start opening a cafe business in the city of Bandung to become a promising place of business.

Entrepreneurs can work if they have high achievement motives which consist of commitment, responsibility, are always optimistic in unfavorable situations and also have the ability to manage proactively. Future orientation is one of the characteristics that must exist in an entrepreneur, this is related to how the continuation of future business development, what plans are needed for businesses that are established in the future. The combination can be in the form of introducing new products or with new qualities, introducing new production methods or methods, opening new markets, obtaining new sources of supply of new materials or components in an industry. The increase and growth of the cafe business cannot be separated from entrepreneurs who can support and see opportunities to develop this business field.

The existence of entrepreneurial cafe owners in the city of Bandung and the importance of the entrepreneurial spirit of entrepreneurs to encourage business success makes them eager to do further research on this matter. When SMEs, especially in the cafe business, are able to apply an entrepreneurial orientation and

innovation, they will be able to develop business strategies so that they can be used as tools to face competition. Because entrepreneurial orientation is one of the important factors that can determine the success of a business.

Entrepreneurial characteristics are seen as having the ability to improve the performance of a business, entrepreneurial characteristics are a very important component in developing a business, it can be seen from the owners and managers in running their businesses that have shown innovative, proactive and courageous behavior in taking risks. Creativity and innovation have different relationships, so creativity is related to useful ideas while innovative ideas are implemented. By maximizing creativity and perspectives and patterns of thinking, you will be able to come up with existing modifications. Innovation has a meaning as renewal by creating something that previously existed and then changes that are better, of higher quality, more attractive, and more in demand than before (Munthe, 2021: 47).

The phenomenon that occurs in SME actors, especially cafe owners in the city of Bandung, is that there are several cafes that are closed/bankrupt even though they have not been around for a long time. This happens because, losing customers. Losing customers makes profits and sales decrease, so business performance declines. This is due to cafe owners losing in competing with their competitors. The cafe owner is not able to provide an attractive location, competitive prices, unique and quality products. In addition, there is no development at the cafe. They do not innovate in various sectors such as products, services, processes, and marketing so that customers can get bored and prefer other places. In addition, the process of learning the characteristics of entrepreneurship is a complex process, because different skills are needed to create or adapt existing knowledge in organizations.

SMEs with an interest in maintaining continuous learning processes gain a better understanding of the market, use their internal knowledge and experience and develop the ability to react quickly to new market needs, flexibly reconfigure their resources and reduce the perception of uncertainty about environmental complexity. Learning includes the acquisition of information on the organization's internal and external environment, its distribution, interpretation and storage for future use in the organization's memory. This process results in the development of organizational knowledge, reflected in shared mental models, databases, formal procedures, routines and formal cultural models that guide organizational behavior. As a result of innovation from the use of new knowledge, *organization learning* is an important element in developing the company's innovative capabilities.

The ability to innovate, transform ideas into new services depends on the skills to acquire and use new knowledge from the internal or external environment (Gottfridsson, 2014), which needs to flow through appropriate distribution and interpretation mechanisms, otherwise it may not be available for innovation purposes. All innovations must contain some level of novelty, in this sense, innovation includes the results of new combinations of existing services, technologies, people and approaches to meet current and prospective customers to build new value propositions or new service systems (Chen et al., 2016), and related to technology adoption. Based on Chen et al. (2016) created an innovation orientation scale to capture the focus

and engagement of service firms on innovation; The scale consists of five categories namely market service *networks*, new services to enterprises, service modifications, service line extensions and new delivery processes, briefly explained that businesses need to launch "new services to market" drive the innovation process as many ideas and knowledge originate of these organizations.

Innovation requires the acquisition and use of knowledge about customers, competitors as well as internal knowledge of the organization's resources and capacities. The level of interaction between entrepreneurs and their clients has been shown to impact the type of knowledge exchanged, as well as the level of customization services developed (Pace and Miles, 2019). Therefore, companies that want to innovate must understand that they are part of a network where they can interact and share resources, knowledge and ideas (Verma & Jayasimha, 2014). Like previous studies that confirmed the positive relationship between organizational learning and innovation (Calantone et al., 2002; Darroch, 2005; Alegre & Chiva, 2008).

The provision of entrepreneurial knowledge includes knowledge about the business being run, how to run the business, knowledge about management, operations, marketing and others. According to Hisrich (Sarwono and Nugroho, 2013:205) "entrepreneurial knowledge is the basis of entrepreneurial resources contained within the individual self". Business owners need to understand knowledge starting with the ability to acquire, develop a business, manage, utilize information, knowledge, and organizational knowledge as well as manage knowledge of workers, then there are three characteristics of how well entrepreneurs carry out activities on knowledge, namely *newness*, *quantity*, and *tacitness*. entrepreneurship as a characteristic or forms of character or character, behavioral patterns, or special signs inherent in every entrepreneur in managing his business to achieve the expected goals. According to Sinaga (2016:25) that the characteristics and character of entrepreneurship must have , confident and optimistic, task and result oriented, dare to take risks and have challenges, have leadership spirit and easily adapt to others and open to suggestions and criticism, originality that is innovative, creative, and flexible, future oriented Attitude or characteristics entrepreneurship is An important part of entrepreneurship, entrepreneurial characteristics will determine success in running and developing a business. From the description of the background, the researchers are interested in conducting research on "The Effect of Entrepreneurial Characteristics on *Innovation Capability* through *Organizational Learning Capability* as an Intervening Variable (Study on Cafe Owners in Bandung City)".

Framework

Entrepreneurial learning is a behavioral and social process in which a person interacts with others trying to recognize and act on opportunities (Rae, 2007). Entrepreneurship learning is not only done in the educational environment itself. It is also recommended that acquiring entrepreneurial knowledge and skills is involved in gaining real-world social experience. The theory of social learning process by Wenger (1998) suggests that one should be actively involved in learning to practice community and build one's identity at the same time. This engagement will shape what they do, who they are and how they interpret what they do in the community. Social participation as a learning and knowing process is characterized by the integration of four

components, namely: meaning (*learning* as experience); practice (learning by doing); community (learning as belonging) and identity (learning as being). This foundation is closely related to what was stated by Rae (2007) that the entrepreneurship learning model contains a social learning process. The social learning process connects individuals with their social context as they develop their identity and entrepreneurial abilities through the environment in which they live (Royo, 2014: 747).

Entrepreneurial characteristics can orient how companies align their processes, practices and managerial activities towards new markets (Lumpkin and Dess 2005). It involves the strategic intentions and actions of entrepreneurs, such as propensity to take risks, level of innovation and ability to recognize opportunities (Smart and Conant 1994). This includes aggressive behavior towards competitors, the choice to act independently and proactively to market (Lumpkin and Dess 2005). Entrepreneurial characteristics also involve a willingness to take risks in pursuing corporate goals, adopting the latest technology and adapting to changes in the business environment (Miles, Arnold and Thompson 1993). Becherer and Maurer (1997) and Prashantham (2004) argue that a high level of entrepreneurial orientation fosters firm growth and expansion, which results in better firm performance.

According to Schumpeter (Ndubisi and Kahraman 2005) there is a difference between adaptive and creative responding to new things. He argues that creative response as a process, in which the industry does something that is beyond the reach of existing practice. He also mentioned that creative responses are influenced by the quality of the available brain and the decisions and behavior of social actors. In the current study, we consider innovation as a creative response from entrepreneurs that is beyond the scope of existing practice for the sample firms. This will depend on the knowledge base of the entrepreneur as well as the desired characteristics to influence the innovation capability of the company. It can be argued that entrepreneurs have been reported in personality and psychological research to exhibit unique characteristics that set them apart from other technology users.

Organizational learning capabilities involve the generation and use of new knowledge that improves organizational performance. Learning is the key to speed and flexibility in the product development process, and systematic learning on the basis of past experiences is very important in the first stage of the product development process (Nederhof et al., 2002). Organizations that are able to generate new knowledge and integrate it with existing knowledge using different methods are expected to perform well in terms of product innovation and manufacturing processes. In addition, the process of developing new products requires continuous organizational renewal (Calantone et al., 2002). In this context, learning ability is seen as a key factor for organizations to innovate (Jerez, 2005; Alegre and Chiva, 2008; Sinkula et al.; Calantone et al.

Figure 1
Research Model

2002). A learning-focused company will have the knowledge and skills to understand and meet customer needs, better analyze competitors' strengths and weaknesses, and be more effective at drawing lessons from failures and successes. Such companies will also be more effective in innovating than their competitors, and innovating more (Garcia-Morales et al. 2007). There are other studies in the literature that examine the relationship between organizational learning ability and product innovation performance. Lynn et al. (1999), for example, found that higher levels of organizational learning were associated with higher success rates in product development. In other words, an increase in organizational learning capability is accompanied by a parallel increase in innovation capability (Hsu and Fang, 2008; Ussahawanitchakit, 2008; Akgün et al. 2007; Phromket and Ussahawanitchakit, 2009). Innovation is an individual and collective learning process that facilitates finding new methods to solve problems, and is associated with learning abilities, which enable organizations to generate, transfer and utilize new knowledge (Alegre and Chiva, 2008; Sinkula et al. 1997; Calantone et al. 2002) . The framework of thought in this research can be seen in the image below:

Research methods

This type of research is a research with a quantitative approach, while based on the objectives, this research uses descriptive and verification methods. The population in this study is the owner of a café in the city of Bandung, using a non- probability sampling technique with a convenience sampling technique, in order to obtain as many as 60 café owners in the city of Bandung as the research sample. Primary data in this study was obtained from the results of distributing questionnaires to 60 cafe owners in the city of Bandung, while secondary data was obtained from literature studies in the form of books, journals, papers, and previous studies related to the problem being studied. The analytical method used is descriptive analysis and data analysis with structural equation modeling (SEM) with partial least squares (PLS) with the help of Smart PLS 3.0 software.

Research Result

Given the data collection is done using a questionnaire, the validity of a research result is largely determined by the measuring instrument used. To measure this in the measurement model (outer model), in this study the validity test uses convergent validity, discriminant validity and reliability testing with construct reliability, where the convergent results obtained indicate that there are two factors in the Entrepreneurial Characteristics variable which are not forming factors, namely on items KK5 and KK6. The results of structural testing (inner model) show that the results of the r-square test, obtained results in innovation capability of 0.353 which are in the strong category, this shows that 35.3% of the percentage of innovation capability can be explained by entrepreneurial characteristics and organizational learning capability , while the value of The rsquare of organizational learning capability obtained is 0.207 which is in the weak category, it shows that 20.7% of the large percentage of organizational learning capability can be explained by entrepreneurial characteristics, and the q-square results show that the results are 0.487 or 48.7% which are in the strong category, so that it can be stated that the amount of diversity of data used in this study is worth 48.7%, while the remaining 51.3% is explained by other variables. Hypothesis testing shows that there is an influence of entrepreneurial

characteristics on organizational learning capability, this is based on the results of the path coefficient direct effect hypothesis testing, the results obtained $t_{\text{statistics}} > t_{\text{table}}$ ($5.351 > 2.002$) and the level of significance (p-value) ($0.000 < 0.05$), then there is the effect of entrepreneurial characteristics on innovation capability, this is based on the results of the path coefficient direct effect hypothesis testing, the results obtained $t_{\text{statistic}} > t_{\text{table}}$ ($2.974 > 2.002$) and a significance level (pvalue) ($0.003 < 0.05$) and there is an effect of organizational learning capability on innovation capability, this is based on the test results The path coefficient direct effect hypothesis is obtained by $t_{\text{statistic}} > t_{\text{table}}$ ($2.384 > 2.002$) and the level of significance (p-value) ($0.018 < 0.05$). While the results of the direct effect test of the effect of the independent variable on the dependent through the intervening variable, show that there is an influence of entrepreneurial characteristics on innovation capability through organizational learning capability, this is based on the indirect effect hypothesis results obtained $t_{\text{statistics}} > t_{\text{table}}$ ($2.105 > 2.002$) and the level of significance (pvalue) ($0.000 < 0.05$).

Conclusion

Based on the results of research on 60 cafe owners in the city of Bandung, and the descriptions that have been carried out in the previous chapter, the researchers conclude that there is an influence of entrepreneurial characteristics on *innovation capability* through *organizational learning capability* on Cafe owners in Bandung City. This shows that the *organizational learning capability* variable is a variable that can affect the entrepreneurial characteristics of *innovation*.

Suggestions

The suggestions that can be given after conducting research are as follows:

1. The results of the research above can be developed into a strategy by cafe owners in the city of Bandung that can increase the success of the business being undertaken. The cafe owner should pay attention to the factors that can affect the success of the business so that they are able and have high competitiveness.
2. Business owners need to pay attention to *organizational learning capability*, because it is a variable that can improve company performance. And also don't forget to innovate because innovation is also a variable that can improve company performance.
3. To cafe owners in the city of Bandung in terms of entrepreneurship, in order to further increase their aggressive attitude in competing such as always taking action before competitors and responding quickly to changes that occur in the environment. In terms of innovation, cafe owners or managers are expected to increase the use of modern machines to support the smooth running of food and beverage production and to make processing time more efficient. Improve the standard of good product quality. In terms of competitive advantage, cafe owners feel the need to pay attention to the quality of product raw materials, in order to further increase their competitive advantage, so that they are superior to their competitors.
4. For further researchers in developing future research by including strategic orientation, knowledge

integration, strategic reactivity, organizational capability, ethnic factors, and focus of study for SMEs.

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